

Coincident transitions across elevation and origins of functional innovations drove the phenotypic and ecological diversity of lungless salamanders

Supplementary Materials

Extended Materials and Methods

Functional innovations in the Plethodontidae

We used the following functional innovations in the main text. Note that this list is not necessarily comprehensive, but is limited to putative innovations posed in the literature and that have clear functional implications for ecology and/or performance. Below we describe each innovation, its phylogenetic distribution, functional utility, and any noteworthy caveats.

Skeletomuscular suite in Desmognathines (*Desmognathus* + *Phaeognathus*) – involves a series of adaptations for feeding and burrowing (following Schwenk and Wake 1992): (1) heavily ossified skull and mandible, (2) dorsoventrally flattened and tapered head, (3) stalked occipital condyles, (4) modified atlas, (5) fortified anterior trunk vertebrae, (6) the presence of atlanto-mandibular ligaments, hypertrophied (7) dorsal spinal and (8) quadrato-pectoralis muscles, and (9) fore- and hindlimb asymmetry, with larger hind limbs. These traits are herein considered adaptations to feeding and burrowing via a head wedging behavior (Schwenk and Wake 1992; Bruce 1996). This innovation is treated as a synapomorphy of Desmognathinae (Schwenk and Wake 1992; Bruce 1996).

Reduced limbs in *Oedipina* (“worm salamanders”) – reduced carpal, tarsal, and phalangeal elements, often including fused digits on both limbs (Brame 1968; Mccranie et al. 2008), herein considered a synapomorphy of *Oedipina* (Brame 1968). Reduced limbs in *Batrachoseps* (“slender salamanders”) (Parra-Olea and Wake 2001; Jockusch et al. 2012). Herein treated as a synapomorphy for *Batrachoseps*, excluding the first diverging lineage within the genus, which has robust limbs (Jockusch et al. 2012; Bonett and Blair 2017). Similar to *Oedipina* in their morphology, but likely achieved via non-paedomorphic means, as the digits are well formed (as opposed to fused in *Oedipina*; Parra-Olea and Wake 2001; Jockusch et al. 2012). In both cases, we consider reduced limbs as an adaptation to a fossorial lifestyle (following Parra-Olea and Wake 2001).

Miniaturization in most *Thorius* (“minute salamanders”) – reduced size, including many skeletal elements, and unique ossification patterns, herein considered an adaptation for exploiting niches in small interstitial spaces not accessible to larger salamanders (Rovito et al. 2013).

Prehensile tail in Bolitoglossines and *Aneides* – the tail can be curled via muscle contraction (Wake 1987). Herein considered an adaptation for climbing or otherwise interacting with the environment by providing enhanced stability and mobility (Wake 1987; Patton et al. 2019; Brown 2020). Note that there are origins of prehensile tails in singular species such as *Plethodon chlorobryonis* (Mittelman 1951) and *Phaeognathus hubrichti* (Blair 1967), which we do not consider in this study due to their origins along terminal branches that lack downstream branches along which to assess rate shifts and microhabitat transitions.

Keeled tail in some *Desmognathus* (the clade comprised by *D. marmoratus*, *D. quadramaculatus*, and *D. folkertsi*; Bruce 1996) and the clade comprised by *Gyrinophilus*, *Pseudotriton*, and *Stereochilus* (Ryan and Bruce 2000). Note that other *Desmognathus* have keeled tails (e.g., *D. brimleyorum*), but these cases are excluded from the analyses due to origins along terminal branches (i.e., within a single species) that lack downstream branches along which to assess rate shifts and microhabitat transitions. Keeled tails improve locomotion performance in aquatic conditions (Fish et al. 2021).

Expanded interdigital webbing in *Bolitoglossa*, *Hydromantes*, and *Chiropterotriton*. Although classically viewed as an adaptation for arboreality (Wake 1987), recently expanded interdigital webbing has instead been linked to a general climbing ability (Baken and Adams 2019). In *Bolitoglossa* expanded interdigital webbing is associated with arboreality (Wake 1987), whereas *Hydromantes* principally inhabit caves, whereas *Chiropterotriton* use a variety of terrestrial, arboreal, and cave microhabitats (Baken and Adams 2019). Herein, we consider the adaptive quality of expanded interdigital webbing as providing an enhanced clinging ability, with a lineage-specific utility (e.g., climbing vegetation or cave walls). Herein considered synapomorphies for each of the three genera, but the extent of interdigital webbing is variable, particularly in *Bolitoglossa* (Baken and Adams 2019).

Indirect (“biphasic”) development in *Desmognathus* (Bruce 1996) and hemidactyline salamanders (Ryan and Bruce 2000). Permits the segregation of larval and adult forms between aquatic and terrestrial environments, thereby reducing intraspecific competition. Note that the innovation in *Desmognathus* excludes *D. wrighti* and *D. organi*. Herein, we treat *D. aeneus* as a reversal to direct development, but note that there is some uncertainty in the phylogenetic position of *D. aeneus* (Bonett and Blair 2017; Jetz and Pyron 2018; Weaver et al. 2020).

Paedomorphy in some *Eurycea* (Bonett and Blair 2017). Other salamanders have some paedomorphic characters (e.g., in the hands and feet; Parra-Olea and Wake 2001 – an innovation encompassed by the previously outlined “reduced limbs” innovation), but here, we restrict the innovation broadly to the respiratory system and its relevance to the water-land boundary (Bonett and Blair 2017; Fabre et al. 2020). Hypothesized to be adaptive in the face of limited resources imposed by caves, where prey is often more prevalent in the aquatic versus terrestrial environment (Weber 2000; Poulson 2012).

The above adaptations are secondary functional innovations that followed the origination of several others early in the evolutionary history of lungless salamanders (i.e., either at or near the root). Given the proximity to the root, we were unable to estimate rate shifts or microhabitat transitions, but for completeness, we describe those innovations below (indicated by light grey in Figure 1 of the main text) since they are referenced in the main text.

Cutaneous respiration in the Plethodontidae – breathing is achieved via gas exchange through thin, moist skin (Spotila and Berman 1976). Although cutaneous respiration evolved before the Plethodontidae, it became the exclusive means for respiration following the evolutionary loss of lungs coincident with the origin of the family (Feder 1983). Lunglessness reduces energetic costs as well as costs related to the growth, development, and maintenance of lungs (Feder 1983). Additionally, lungless stream salamanders (e.g., *Desmognathus*, *Eurycea*, *Gyrinophilus*, *Pseudotriton*) benefit by not having to invest energy into compensatory mechanisms to counteract buoyancy and locomotion hinderances created by lungs (Wassersug and Feder 1983).

Direct development in the Plethodontidae – involves the loss of an aquatic life stage in which eggs are laid on land and hatch as small adult forms (Bonett and Blair 2017). Herein considered an adaptation for

exploiting the terrestrial realm without requiring access to aquatic conditions for reproduction (Wake and Hanken 2004). The origin of direct development has been well resolved at the base of the Plethodontidae (Bonett and Blair 2017), but note that this innovation has been subsequently lost several times within the family (Chippindale et al. 2004; Bonett and Blair 2017; Weaver et al. 2020).

Nasolabial groove in the Plethodontidae – provide enhanced olfaction and also functions to drain and prevent blockage of the nares in dry and wet conditions (Brown and Martof 1966). Herein considered an adaptation for dynamically moving back and forth between terrestrial and aquatic conditions or living principally along the boundary between both habitats (Brown and Martof 1966). In addition to the draining function, nasolabial grooves are sexually dimorphic and likely play an important role in chemoreception during mating. As such, the grooves function in promoting courtship in the terrestrial habitat as opposed to aquatic (Brown 1968; Dawley and Bass 1989). Nasolabial grooves are a synapomorphy of the Plethodontidae (Brown and Martof 1966).

Spring-powered tongue-protrusion (“ballistic tongue protrusion”) – a derived modification of the ancestral muscle-powered condition. Ballistic mechanisms are less thermally sensitive than muscle-powered tongue-protrusion, thus providing enhanced performance in cooler conditions such as montane environments (Deban and Scales 2016; Deban et al. 2020). Herein considered a synapomorphy of bolitoglossines, with a separate origin in *Hydromantes* (following Deban et al. 2020). Note that another independent origin in a singular species, *Ensatina* (Deban et al. 2020), is not considered in this study due to its limited macroevolution scale (and inability to assess rate shifts and microhabitat transitions on downstream branches).

Microhabitat classifications and related uncertainty

We present a slightly modified version of Baken and Adams (2019) “7-M” delimitation scheme. In general, we were slightly more conservative with fossorial and aquatic designations (often using terrestrial instead of fossorial and semi-aquatic instead of aquatic) as well as fixing some errors (e.g., *Phaeognathus* is definitely fossorial; Dodd 1991; Gunzburger and Guyer 1998; Bakkegard 2002), as well as incorporating feedback on microhabitat classifications from eight plethodontid experts (see Acknowledgements). Microhabitat classifications were defined as follows (if biphasic, categories refer to the adult stage):

Terrestrial species occur principally along the ground, often underneath a cover object such as a rock, log, or leaf litter (includes species that dwell on moss if the moss occurs along the ground). These species rarely occur along elevated/vertical plants, underground, or in water.

Arboreal species spend a significant amount of time on plants with vertical structure such as bromeliads or ferns (does not include plants distributed purely along the ground such as moss).

Fossorial species spend a significant amount of time underground in burrows (must extend beyond short seasonal periods, otherwise considered “terrestrial”).

Saxicolous species have an affinity for rocky habitats such as rocky outcroppings and otherwise occur in terrestrial conditions.

Aquatic species are restricted to water (i.e., do not metamorphose; perform gas exchange via gills).

Semiaquatic species spend a significant amount of time in water (stream channels or margins, springs, or seepage) but metamorphose and are not restricted to water; occasionally occupy terrestrial habitats immediately adjacent to water.

Cave species principally occupy caves, including the mouths of caves and immediate vicinity; includes species that generously occupy surface and subterranean habitats. Does not include species that have a limited occupation around the mouths of caves (e.g., *Aneides aeneus*, *Eurycea longicauda*, etc.)

We also allowed for alternative microhabitat delimitation where appropriate. For example, many paedomorphic species are both aquatic and cave-adapted; therefore, we used “cave” as an alternative designation for any relevant species (see Figure 1 in the main text). Owing to differing opinions about salamander microhabitat use and general uncertainty with many species, we summarize our results across all six alternative coding schemes presented by Baken and Adams (2019) as well as our modified classification scheme to account for any feasible microhabitat transitions. Note that none of the rate (MuSSCRat or rate-by-state tests) or disparity analyses in the main text are informed a priori by the microhabitat classifications. We only use them to interpret the results and associate transitions with rate shifts, which are summarized in Figure 4 and Table 1 in the main text.

Relationship between rates of phenotypic evolution and elevation

In the main text, we estimated the rates of phenotypic evolution using a state-dependent, relaxed model of Brownian motion (BM) (May and Moore 2020). To assess the robustness of our results, we repeated these analyses across random local clock (RLC) models with different priors on the number of rate shifts (*i.e.*, 1, 25, 50, 75, and 100 shifts). We also estimated rates using an alternative Uncorrelated lognormal model (UCLN) in which the rates do not have phylogenetic structure (rates have phylogenetic structure if estimated with the RLC model). Using all these alternative models, we consistently found that the rates of salamander phenotypic evolution were state-dependent (all posterior probability; PP = 1.0; Figure S1).

We further scrutinized the robustness of our results by using a different method. The MuSSCRat model (May and Moore 2020) necessitated converting elevation, a continuous character, into a discrete character (*i.e.*, elevation quartiles). We used an alternative method that allowed treating elevation as a continuous character. To this end, we employed the rate-by-state test (modified from Reynolds et al. 2016) to determine if rates of phenotypic evolution were correlated with elevation. In this procedure, multivariate standardized contrasts (McPeck et al. 2008) of body shape were regressed against the ancestral state of elevation. Standardized contrasts were calculated using the *pic* function in *ape* (Paradis et al. 2004). The ancestral states of \ln -transformed elevation (m) were calculated using the *fastAnc* function in *phytools* (Revell 2012), which estimates the ancestral states at internal nodes of the phylogeny using maximum likelihood (Felsenstein 1985). To determine if the effect size (correlation coefficient) of the observed traits were beyond those expected from a null Brownian motion model of evolution, we constructed a null distribution of effect sizes by simulating 100 sets of traits using the *fastBM* function in *phytools* (Revell 2012) and repeating the phylogenetic independent contrasts and rate-by-state tests for these simulated datasets. We also estimated species-specific rates of diversification, or tip rates, to characterize rates of phenotypic evolution (Harvey and Rabosky 2018; Title and Rabosky 2019). Tip rates are an estimate of present-day evolutionary rate, conditioned on past evolutionary history (Title and Rabosky 2019). We calculated tip rates using a multivariate relaxed Brownian motion with a RLC (May and Moore 2020; Burress et al. 2020; Burress and Muñoz 2021). Statistical significance was assessed using phylogenetic generalized least squares (pGLS) implemented with the *gls* function in the *nlme* package (Pinheiro et al. 2017).

We found that rates of salamander phenotypic evolution, estimated with multivariate contrasts, were negatively correlated with elevation ($r = 0.197$; $f = 12.21$; $P < 0.001$) and that this effect size was well beyond those expected from a null Brownian motion process (Figure S2) and robust to the exclusion of outliers (i.e., beyond the 95% C.I.; $P < 0.05$). This result is consistent with the MuSSCRat model in which rates of evolution were faster in lower elevation quartiles (Figure 4 and S1). In contrast, rates of salamander phenotypic evolution, estimated with tip rates, was not correlated with elevation ($r = 0.0019$; $t = 1.11$; $p = 0.267$); suggesting that phenotypic evolution in response to the elevational gradient originates deep in the phylogeny, rather than from contemporary diversification.

Supplementary Tables and Figures

Table S1. Model fitting among transition models that describe microhabitat evolution in lungless salamanders. The row in bold is the best fitting model according to AICc. Abbreviations: Equal rates (ER), symmetrical rates (SYM), all rates different (ARD), sample size corrected Akaike information criterion (AICc).

Model	Rate categories	Log-likelihood	AICc
ER	rate1	-326.27	654.56
ER	rate2	-326.28	660.68
SYM	rate1	-263.85	572.95
SYM	rate2	-253.86	610.88
ARD	rate1	-246.13	589.99
ARD	rate2	-238.34	717.01

Figure S1. Species richness (left panel) and elevation (right panel) across the distribution of plethodontid salamanders. Illustrations depict a species from the indicated geographic region. The inset in the right panel depicts species richness across the elevational gradient.

Figure S2. Evolutionary history of the elevational (midpoint) distribution of plethodontid salamanders (A). The ancestral states were estimated with Maximum likelihood in the contMap function in phytools (Revell 2012). Distribution of elevation (midpoint) among species (B). Bars reflect the three discretization schemes used for elevation described in the text: the lower and upper 50th percentiles, lowland (<1068.5m) and highland (>1068.5m); the lower, mid, and upper 33rd percentiles, lowland (<796.3m), midland (7.96.3-1465.6m), and highland (>1465.6m); and four quartiles, lowland (<640m), midlow (641-1069m), midhigh (1070m-1689m), and highland (>1690m). Compare with results shown in Figures S6-8.

Figure S3. Diagram depicting the assessment of coincident and delayed rate shifts. Hypothetical scenario in which a functional innovation (shown in red) is a synapomorphy of a clade (highlighted in gray). An ancestral state reconstruction would highlight the most recent common ancestor of the clade as the origin of the innovation (delineating the “focal clade”); however, the true origin would naturally lie along the rootward branch (b_c). Therefore, we consider rate shifts along b_c as *coincident* with the origination of the functional innovation. To also account for evolutionary lag, we consider *delayed* rate shifts along up to two tipward branches (b_d). The same assessment was applied to microhabitat transitions.

Figure S4. Statistical independence of rate and state using limb length as an example (reduced limbs). We interrogated the non-independence of phenotype and rate directly following the same workflow used in the main text (i.e., the rate-by-state analyses depicted in Figure 2). The multivariate evolutionary rate of forelimb length is not correlated with limb length (residuals) using phylogenetic contrasts or tip rates (all $P > 0.446$). Therefore, although limb length is a trait used to calculate the multivariate evolutionary rate in the main text, its evolutionary rate is independent of its state (i.e., it is statistically unproblematic as an innovation; ‘reduced limbs’).

Figure S5. Trait correlations for all pairs of traits, as estimated with MuSSCRat (May & Moore, 2020). These correlations were used to inform the simulated datasets (see main text). During this procedure, we arbitrarily used the values from the model with a prior of 100 rate shifts; trait correlations from the model with the lowest and highest prior on the number of rate shifts are shown to demonstrate that the estimates are equivalent. The dashed line depicts a 1-to-1 relationship.

Figure S6. Rates of salamander phenotypic evolution across elevation quartiles, estimated with a random local clock model in MuSSCRat (May and Moore 2020) across different prior numbers of rate shifts. Colors depict the elevation quartile: lowland (blue), midlow (yellow), midhigh (orange), and highland (red). All models have posterior probability = 1.0.

Figure S7. Rates of salamander phenotypic evolution across elevation quartiles, estimated with an uncorrelated lognormal model in MuSSCRat (May and Moore 2020). Colors depict the elevation quartile: lowland (blue), midlow (yellow), midhigh (orange), and highland (red). Posterior probability = 1.0. Compare with the results using a Random Local Clock model depicted in Figure 2a in the main text.

Figure S8. Sensitivity of the MuSSCRat analyses to different numbers of state in the discrete character (i.e., different resolution when discretizing elevation). Using 2, 3, or 4 discrete states to represent elevation resulted in unanimous support for faster rates of phenotypic evolution in lowlands. Posterior probability (PP) that the rates are state-dependent is inset for each model.

background_rates
0.0101

Figure S9. Branch-specific background rates of phenotypic evolution across the plethodontid phylogeny. Background rates reflect rate heterogeneity not attributable to elevation (compare with Figure 1 in the main text).

Figure S10. Trait-specific rates of evolution in lungless salamanders, as estimated with MuSSCRat. Distributions reflect the range of estimates across 100,000 iterations. Rates are summarized from a single model, but the trait-specific rates were visually identical across all models.

State-dependent phenotypic rate (branches of phylogeny)

Figure S11. The origins of functional innovations across the plethodontid phylogeny. Posterior probability (PP) of innovation-associated rate shifts is labeled with text. Reference Figure 1 for tip names. Note that the rate shift associated with miniaturization in *Thorius* (light blue; PP=0.86) is not labeled because the shift occurred in rates of background variation (not rates as they respond to elevation as shown here).

Figure S12. Posterior probability (PP) of rate shifts across models with different priors on the number of shifts (A). The support for rate shifts waned with priors of fewer rate shifts, but rate shifts along innovation-associated branches were concentrated in the 99th and 95th percentiles across models with different priors (A). Posterior support for most branches followed this pattern, as they fell below the 1:1 line (dashed lines in B). Compare to Figure 3 in the main text.

Figure S13. Microhabitat and phenotypic diversity across the elevational gradient summarized (averaged) across six different coding schemes presented by Baken and Adams (2019): the number of microhabitat specialists (a) and phenotypic disparity (b). The x-axis depicts the four elevation quartiles (low; Q1 to high; Q4).

Figure S14. Distribution of traits across microhabitat types (mean \pm 95% C.I.). With only one exception (wide bodies in arboreal species), the phenotypic extremes of each trait are found in a microhabitat type that is lost at high elevation.

A

B

Figure S15. Ancestral state reconstruction of microhabitat use in lungless salamanders (A). Pies at internal nodes denote the proportion of character states across 1000 stochastic histories. Note that “cave” is painted the same color across the plot, but was coded as a polymorphic state (i.e., associated with several microhabitats; see Figure 1). Transition matrix showing the relative transition rates among character states (B; warmer colors reflect higher transition rate).

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